

Subcellular Fraction	Bio. Rep.	Tech. Rep.	LMB treated	Bio. Rep.	Tech. Rep.	Control
Cytoplasm	1	1	Yael-Cyto-LMB1-1-20210830	1	1	Yael-Cyto-Ctrl1-1-20210827
		2	Yael-Cyto-LMB1-2-20210910		2	Yael-Cyto-Ctrl1-2-20210909
	2	1	Yael-Cyto-LMB2-1-20210901	2	1	Yael-Cyto-Ctrl2-1-20210831
		2	Yael-Cyto-LMB2-2-20210913		2	Yael-Cyto-Ctrl2-2-20210910
Nucleoplasm	1	1	Yael-NP-LMB1-1-20210902	1	1	Yael-NP-Ctrl1-1-20210902
		2	Yael-NP-LMB1-2-20210908		2	Yael-NP-Ctrl1-2-20210908
	2	1	Yael-NP-LMB2-1-20210907	2	1	Yael-NP-Ctrl2-1-20210903
		2	Yael-NP-LMB2-2-20210907		2	Yael-NP-Ctrl2-2-20210903
Nuclear Envelope	1	1	Yael-NE-LMB1-1-20211208	1	1	Yael-NE-Ctrl1-1-20211201
		2	Yael-NE-LMB1-2-20211210		2	Yael-NE-Ctrl1-2-20211202
	2			2	1	Yael-NE-Ctrl2-1-20211203
		2	Yael-NE-LMB2-2-20211214		2	Yael-NE-Ctrl2-2-20211207
Membrane				1	1	Yael-MEM-Ctrl1-1-20221110
					2	Yael-MEM-Ctrl1-2-20221114
				2	1	Yael-MEM-Ctrl2-1-20221111
					2	Yael-MEM-Ctrl2-2-20221115